

ISic0871

I.Sicily inscription 0871

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble (grey)

Object

sarcophagus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Poss. Catacomb of S. Maria di Gesu

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 5638

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Φρετηνσία · Στατία Σκρειβωνία
2. ἔζησεν ἀμέμπτως · καὶ σεμνῶς
3. ἔτη λγ μῆν(ας) η ἡμέρ(ας) κδ

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491440

EDCS 39102025

PHI 140349

PHI 175707

Bibliography

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